

Relationship between Administrators' Supervision and Staff's Job Performance: A Case Study of Higher Institutions in Sokoto Central, Sokoto State Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The management of both academic and administrative activities of schools usually falls under the responsibilities of the management. One of the principal's responsibilities in the management is to supervise and articulate activities in order to achieve quality education for the overall benefit of the society. Management of properties is compulsory and which is also the responsibility lies solely to those who were assign to discharge the control and maintenance of any aspect. Managements' supervision is the totality effort to ensure positive and satisfaction in delivery of academic activities of both human and material resources in an institution. Whereas staffs as we know are part of human resources who were train skilfully to deliver the academic and non-academic activities firmly under the supervision of the management in the institutions. The main objective of this paper is to find out the relationship between administrators' supervision and staff's job performance in high institutions in Sokoto state Nigeria. Null hypothesis has set to determine the relationship between administrators' supervision and staffs' job performance. The study use a descriptive survey of the correlational research type in order to collect data on, and quantitative approach was used because the data were analysed statistically. The populations of this study were all the government high institutions in the six (6) local government areas from the Sokoto Central. The central consisted of eight (8) high institutions. The participants were purposively sampled and 291 participants were considered. Two type of self-constructed questionnaire titled: Managements' Supervision Measurement Scale (PSS) and Staffs' Job Performance Rating Scale (TJPRS) based on five (5) points rating agreement. Specifically, descriptive statistics was used to analyze the data. Pearson Product moment correlation coefficient (PPMCC) was used to test the hypotheses formulated in the study, so as to highlight the level of relationship which exist between managements' supervision and staffs' job performance in high institutions. The findings of the study indicated that there is high level of management supervision in the institutions in Sokoto state. It also indicated that there is significance relationship between the management' supervision and staffs' job performance in the institutions in Sokoto state and three (3) of the null hypotheses were rejected. The study recommended that school managements should accurately supervise the academic activities for proper delivery of responsibilities and effective job satisfaction. They should also create more capacity building such as retraining of their staff to enhance enforcement of the regulation of policy, conduct of staffs and students, and their punctuality for effective job performance.

Keywords: Managements, Supervision, Staff, Job Performance and Institutions

INTRODUCTION

The management of both academic and administrative activities of schools usually falls under the responsibilities of the principal officers in an institution. One of the principals' responsibilities in the management of the institution is to supervise and articulate activities in order to achieve quality education for the overall benefit of the society. Leaders' supervision is the totality effort to ensure positive and satisfaction in delivery of academic activities of both human and material resources in the school. Whereas teachers as we know are part of human resources who were train skilfully to deliver the teaching and learning activities firmly under the supervision of the principal. According to Nwagwu in Manga (2018) the legal duties of school administrators include the formulation of plans and policies; enforcement of rules and regulations that will guide the activities and conduct of staff and students; assigning duties, tasks and responsibilities to teachers and nonteaching staff; directing all academics and co-curricular activities and supervision of all school personnel. Similarly, Fuller (2009) in Manga (2018) stated that the primary duty of teachers is to teach efficiently and effectively.

Supervision is an administrative process through which the leader ensures that his subordinates are all contributing towards effective learning process. Hammock, Owing and Nwaogu in Agih (2015) stated that supervision attempts to look into the organization of learning programs, the grouping of pupils, method of evaluating, reporting and determining pupil's progress, the content of the curriculum, the teaching methods, the philosophy and practicing of discipline, the time schedule, place and procedure of staff meetings, procedures used in parents conference, the study and use of the community resources. All these are evaluated and thoroughly discussed in the attempt to improve the learning and growing of the students.

Castler in Egboka (2018) in order to execute the administrative functions for achievement of the objectives of secondary education, the principals must apply certain management strategies. That is to say, principals should provide management supportive strategies that will improve other school personnel work quality and the utilization of available professional and material resources for achieving educational objectives in secondary schools as well as supervision. Managements should further provide teachers with needed management supports to effectively function in their schools. In addition, Akubue cited in Onuma (2016) affirmed that the provision of management support strategies to staff involve giving supportive instructional supervision, adequate welfare, rewards, in-service education program as and when due.

However, the concept of supervision is one that describes a process that is common to all professions and occupations. No organization can function effectively without it. Supervision is an interaction between at least two persons for the improvement of activity. It is a formative, supportive and developmental process designed to improve and process of guiding encouraging, directing and motivating workers so as to improve their output. Murtiningsih, et al (2019) stated that the supervision orientation can be said as a process of assistance in developing teaching and learning situations to obtain better conditions, and this examination is intended to see how the activities carried out have reached the goal. The desired expectation is that the academic quality of the teacher increases through academic supervision. Irfan (2018) argues that the academic supervision of school principals provides a very important role and influence on the teaching performance of teachers because it gives an influence on improving the quality of teacher teaching resulting from the coaching and improvement of aspects of learning needed by teachers, can also be an encouragement morally to progress so that the teacher always makes improvements to the quality of teaching which is the main task of a teacher.

Statement Of The Problem

School environment operates based on formal setting and rules upon each activities, thus it is viable for the success of academic activities to be supervised regularly so as to maintain the stated aims and objectives of the education. In other hand, staffs are expected to discharge their duties in the institution through maintaining the regulations concerning academics and other routines through the supervision of the managements in the school. There are numerous duties which are needed for the staffs to perform as part of their job in the school under the supervision of the managements. Manga (2018) outlined staff's

legal duties to include exercising reasonable care to ensure the safety and security of students under their care; discipline erring students; render community service in their area of specialization; as well as maintenance of institution property and facilities in their care. Many factors have been reported such as negligence on responsibilities in school which might lead to poor management of school (Hayab, Felicia & Victor, 2023). This is why the researcher feels interested to carry out this study to find out the relationship that exists between managements' supervision and staffs' job performance in high institutions in Sokoto state Nigeria.

Objectives Of The Study

The main objective of this study is to find out the relationship between managements' supervision and staffs' job performance in high institutions in Sokoto state Nigeria, other objectives of the study include:

1. To determine the regularity of managements' instructional supervision in high institutions in Sokoto state
2. To examine the regularity of managements' facilities supervision in high institutions in Sokoto state
3. To find out the regularity of managements' punctuality supervision in high institution in Sokoto state

Research Questions

1. What is the level of regularity of managements' instructional supervision and staffs' job performance in high institutions in Sokoto state?
2. What is the level regularity of managements' facilities supervision and staffs' job performance in high institutions in Sokoto state?
3. What is the level of regularity of managements' punctuality supervision and staffs' job performance in high institutions in Sokoto state?

Research Hypotheses

H₀1: There is no significant relationship between managements' instructional supervision and staffs' job performance in high institutions in in Sokoto state

H₀2: There is no significant relationship between managements' facilities supervision and staffs' job performance in high institutions in Sokoto state

H₀3: There is no significant relationship between managements' punctuality supervision and staffs' job performance in high institutions in Sokoto state

RELATED LITERATURE REVIEW

Instructional Supervision

Adeyemi (2018) explains that instructional supervision is the process of administration which involves the push to manage everyday activities of individual or group of people working in the school system. The principal is the leader and observes, the leader in any group is considered as having the best ideas, possessing the greatest understanding of situations and providing the best guidance. Bernard and Goodyear in Maria (2018) visualize instructional supervision as "a counseling intervention that is given by a senior individual from a calling to a lesser part or individuals from that same calling. The relationship is evaluative and stretches out after some time and has the concurrent reason for upgrading the expert working of the lesser part / members. It is expected to monitor the quality of the professional service they give and also serve as a guardian to the individuals who are to enter that profession.

Maria (2018) clarifies that principals' instructional supervision is essential to teachers' effectiveness because it offers the professional support and guidance that enables them perform their best. It is a form of instructional leadership and its aim is to ensure qualitative learning in the school. Supervision of learning enables the principal to monitor the performance of his teaching staff with the aim of identifying the merits and demerits and utilizing befitting and genial systems to rectify the blemishes and

enhance the benefits. Along these lines, the teachers are increasingly availed of the opportunity to become better. It is a process of stimulating growth and excellence in teaching.

Instructional supervision is an administrative process through which the leader ensures that his subordinates are all contributing towards effective learning process. Hammock and Owing in Agabi (2015) stated that instructional supervision attempts to look into the organization of learning programs, the grouping of pupils, method of evaluating, reporting and determining pupil's progress, the content of the curriculum, the teaching methods, the philosophy and practicing of discipline, the time schedule, place and procedure of staff meetings, procedures used in parents conference, the study and use of the community resources. All these are evaluated and thoroughly discussed in the attempt to improve the learning and growing of the students.

According to Agabi, Agbor and Ololube (2015) the concept of instructional supervision is one that describes a process that is common to all professions and occupations. No organization can function effectively without it. Supervision is an interaction between at least two persons for the improvement of activity. It is a formative, supportive and developmental process designed to improve and process of guiding encouraging, directing and motivating workers so as to improve their output. The author further stated that there are many things to supervise. These include the school program and resources, assessment of Principals (other head teachers), the teachers, the non-academic staff, the students/ Pupils, the school plants (facilities and equipment), the school account, and the school project and school records. Also, the indicators of quality in education as discussed in the proceeding text are others items to supervise.

Facilities Supervision

Nwogu in Chinyere (2023) define classroom supervision as the process of bringing about improvement in instruction by working with people who are working with pupils in classroom, as a matter of fact, classroom supervision is concerned with the improvement of teaching and learning in order to ensure quality services rendered to educational clients; thereby achieving educational objectives. Simply put, school supervision is the process of bringing about improvement in teachers' performance and students' active participation in the classroom. Thus, classroom supervision is primarily aimed at developing teachers towards positive attitudes and pedagogical skills that will enable them to achieve excellence in teaching. Nosiri (2017) stated that, classroom supervision is used to describe those activities which are primarily and directly concerned with studying and improving the conditions which surround learning and teaching. Classroom supervision deals mainly with improvement of teaching and learning. Classroom supervision is necessary in schools because it monitors, guides and stimulates optimal utilization of limited educational resources for achievement of educational objectives. It helps teachers to recognize and accept general aims, help them see beyond the present performance and seek improvement; to identify and coordinate efforts and resources for more efficient and greater impact on important educational problems; to increase the amount and quality of learning by students and to promote continuous appraisal of performance of all who emerge in the educational process.

Okefor, (2021) revealed that classroom supervision has a positive relationship with teachers' level of commitment and dedication in school programs and activities. Ibeabuchi, (2021) stated that in classroom supervision the principals ascertain the level of cooperation, collaboration, and synergy as well as talent management among the paired teachers in the quest to deliver quality instruction to the students. The principals also supervise their level of compatibility and agreeableness in time management and students assessment. Therefore, proper team teaching supervision can lead to effective and efficient school organization.

According to Renata, Wardiah and Kristiawan (2018) the classroom supervision can be said is a process of assistance in developing teaching and learning situations to obtain better conditions, and this is intended to see how the activities carried out have reached the goal. The desired expectation is that the academic quality of the teacher increases through classroom supervision. In this case, capacity building is not merely an increase in teacher knowledge and teaching skills, but also in increasing teacher

commitment or willingness or motivation, because if the teacher's work abilities and motivation increases, the quality of learning will increase. Furthermore, Irfan (2018) argues that the classroom supervision of school principals provides a very important role and influence on the teaching performance of teachers because it gives an influence on improving the quality of teacher teaching resulting from the coaching and improvement of aspects of learning needed by teachers, can also be an encouragement morally to progress so that the teacher always makes improvements to the quality of teaching which is the main task of a teacher.

Punctuality Supervision

According to Okoye, Onyali, & Ezeugbor, (2016) punctuality supervision is the most prominent task of the school principal which is to improve the teaching-learning process through effective quality control measures that are connected to teachers' class attendance. It is the primary responsibility of the school principal to coordinate and control teachers' activities for the purpose of achieving the best in the management of instructional resource inputs, process and outputs which determine students' academic success in secondary schools.

Supportive school environment especially teachers may play an important role in improving punctuality and time management skills for student's academic success. Time management issue is also influenced by perception and behaviors on how individuals perceive and think about managing their time. According to Nupur (2020) punctuality supervision among the teachers is the reflection of self-discipline and devotion to work and give knowledge to the students. Students are impressed with the teachers, they learn from them. The teachers should be punctuality so that the students learn the same from them, learning gets easier. Aji et al. (2016) stated that the success of achieving educational goals is not solely dependent on providing teaching programs. The program needs to be supported by motivation, management systems, education administration, and supervision. In this matter, the educational process's implementation can achieve optimal results if the principal focuses more on the punctuality supervision of the teacher. In this case, a teacher is the implementer of the educational program operationalization. Nevertheless, in practice, the teacher may develop innovations in carrying out their duties. In other words, innovative performance is essential.

METHODOLOGY

This study used a descriptive survey of the correlational research type in order to collect data on managements' supervision and staffs' job performance in high institutions in Sokoto state, and quantitative approach was used because the data analysis technique were statistically in nature for the purpose to test the hypotheses that have been set. According to Creswell and Creswell (2018) the design enables researcher to ascertain the extent to which a variation in one variable is associated with variation in another. Therefore, correlational design was adopted in the conduct of this study since the researcher is interested in establish a relationship between variables which are managements' supervision and staffs' job performance in high institutions in Sokoto state. The populations of this study were all the government high institutions in the six (6) local government areas from the Sokoto Central. The central consisted of eight (8) high institutions. The participants were purposively sampled from the eight (8) public tertiary institution within the Sokoto central. 291 participants were considered in the selected institutions. Two type self-constructed questionnaire titled: Managements' Supervision Measurement Scale (PSS) and Staffs' Job Performance Rating Scale (TJPRS) based on five (5) points rating agreement. Specifically, descriptive statistics (frequency and percentage) was used to analyze the data obtained from the research questions. Pearson Product moment correlation coefficient (PPMCC) was used to test the hypotheses formulated in the study, so as to highlight the level of relationship which may exist between managements' supervision and staffs' job performance in high institutions. The two questionnaire were constructed based on five (5) points rating scale; 5.0 = 70%-100% Very High Level, 4.0 = 60%-69% High Level, 3.0 = 50%-59% Moderate Level, 2.0 = 40%- 49% Low Level, 1.0= 0-39% Very Low Level

was used to obtain information need for this research. 3.0 and above is the cut off points of satisfactory condition while below 3.0 is unsatisfactory.

RESULT

The research questions were answered as follows:

Research Question 1: *What is the Level of regularity of managements' instructional supervision in high institutions in Sokoto state?*

Table 1: Level of Regularity of Managements' Instructional Supervision in High Institutions in Sokoto State

S/No	Items	Frequency	%	\bar{x}	Level	Decision
1.	Lecture attendance	195	64%	4.0	HL	Satisfactory
2.	Students management	202	67%	4.0	HL	Satisfactory
3.	Lecture hall control	178	56%	3.0	ML	Satisfactory
4.	Regular Assessment	211	69%	4.0	HL	Satisfactory
5.	Preparation of Materials	223	75%	5.0	VHL	Satisfactory
6.	Coordination of lectures	171	57%	3.0	ML	Satisfactory
7.	Student/Lecturer attitude	174	58%	3.0	ML	Satisfactory
8.	Familiarization with course	183	59%	3.0	ML	Satisfactory
9.	Record keeping	174	58%	3.0	ML	Satisfactory
10.	Preparation of exams	234	78%	5.0	VHL	Satisfactory

Source: Primary Data (2024)

Table 1 shows that item 10 and 5 of instructional supervision having 78% and 75% are above 3.0 points of satisfaction at the very high level; item 4, 2 and 1 of the instructional supervision having 69%, 67% and 64% are above 3.0 points of satisfaction at high level, while item 8, 3, 9, 7 and 6 of instructional supervision having 59%, 58%, 58%, 57% and 56% are at 3.0 points of satisfaction at moderate level. Considering the majority of the responses of the respondents fall above the 3.0 cut off points of satisfaction, therefore, it is an indication that the instructional supervision is at the very high level of maintenance. This also means that managements' supervision of instruction in high institutions in Sokoto state is at high level.

Research Question 2: *What is the Level of regularity of managements' facilities supervision in high institutions in Sokoto state?*

Table 4 Level of regularity of managements' facilities supervision in high institutions in Sokoto state

S/No	Items	Frequency	%	\bar{x}	Level	Decision
1.	Roof of Building	186	62%	4.0	HL	Satisfactory
2.	Buildings repainting	184	61%	4.0	HL	Satisfactory
3.	Building walls	184	61%	4.0	HL	Satisfactory
4.	Floor of Buildings	255	92%	5.0	VHL	Satisfactory
5.	Windows condition	213	71%	5.0	VHL	Satisfactory
6.	Doors condition	213	71%	5.0	VHL	Satisfactory
7.	Student and lecturers Seats	214	71%	5.0	VHL	Satisfactory
8.	Ceiling of Buildings	255	92%	5.0	VHL	Satisfactory
9.	Chalkboard/Whiteboard	184	62%	4.0	HL	Satisfactory
10.	Ceiling Fans	184	62%	4.0	HL	Satisfactory

Source: Primary Data (2023)

Table 4 shows that item 4, 8, 5, 6 and 7 of buildings having 92%, 92%, 72%, 71%, 71%, 71% are above 3.0 points of satisfaction at the very high level; item 1, 9, 10, 2 and 3 of the buildings having 62%, 62% , 62%, 61%, and 61% are also above 3.0 points of satisfaction at high level, while. Considering the majority of the responses of the respondents fall above the 3.0 cut off points of satisfaction, therefore, it is an indication that the buildings are at the very high level of management. This also means that management of buildings in high institutions in Sokoto state is at very high level.

Research Question 3: *What is the level of regularity of managements' punctuality supervision in high institutions in Sokoto state?*

Table 5 Level of regularity of managements' punctuality supervision in high institutions in Sokoto state

S/No	Items	Frequency	%	\bar{x}	Level	Decision
1.	Attend lecture in time	174	59%	3.0	ML	Satisfactory
2.	Submit C.A in time	183	69%	4.0	HL	Satisfactory
3.	Attendance of meeting	184	70%	5.0	VHL	Satisfactory
4.	Distribute material regularly	260	87%	5.0	VHL	Satisfactory
5.	Organizing seminars regularly	209	70%	5.0	VHL	Satisfactory
6.	Assessing students at regular time	209	70%	5.0	VHL	Satisfactory
7.	Following schedules accordingly	212	73%	5.0	VHL	Satisfactory
8.	Perform responsibilities as schedule	257	84%	5.0	VHL	Satisfactory
9.	Preservation of source	173	58%	3.0	ML	Satisfactory
10.	Marking script at prompt time	183	69%	4.0	HL	Satisfactory

Source: Primary Data (2023)

Table 5 shows that item 4, 8, 7, 5, 6 and 3 of punctuality having 87% 84%, 73%, 70% and another 70% are above 3.0 points of satisfaction at the very high level; item 2 and 10 of the punctuality having 69% and 69% are above 3.0 points of satisfaction at high level, while item 1, and 9, of punctuality having 59%, and 58%, are at 3.0 points of satisfaction at moderate level. Considering the majority of the responses of the respondents fall above the 3.0 cut off points of satisfaction, therefore, it is an indication that the punctuality are at the very high level of management. This also means that managements' supervision of punctuality in high institutions in Sokoto state is at very high level.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis 1: H_{01} :

There is no significant relationship between managements' instructional supervision and staffs' job performance in high institutions in in Sokoto state

Table 6: Relationship between Managements' Instructional Supervision and Staffs' Job Performance in High Institutions in Sokoto state

Variable	N	\bar{x}	Df	Sig-Value	P-Value	Decision
Instructional Supervision	291	1.0		0.05	0.00	1.00
Job Performance	291	0.00				H_0 Rejected

Source: Primary Data (2024)

Table 6 show that at 0.05 level of accuracy, the computed sig-value 0.00 and P-value 1.00 respectively; since the computed P-value is greater than the tabulated value, thus the hypothesis was rejected. Thus there is relationship between managements' instructional supervision and staffs' job performance in high institutions in in Sokoto state.

Hypothesis 2: H₀₂:

There is no significant relationship between managements' facilities supervision and staffs' job performance in high institutions in Sokoto state

Table 7: Relationship between Managements' Facilities Supervision and Staffs' Job Performance in High Institutions in Sokoto state

Variable	N	\bar{x}	Df	Sig-Value	P-Value	Decision
Facilities Supervision	291	1.0	0.05	0.00	0.55	H ₀ Rejected
Job Performance	291	0.00				

Source: Primary Data (2024)

Table 10 show that at 0.05 level of accuracy, the computed values are sig-value 0.00 and P-value 0.55 respectively; since the computed P-value is greater than the tabulated value, the hypothesis was rejected. Thus there is relationship between managements' facilities supervision and staffs' job performance in high institutions in Sokoto state.

Hypothesis 3: H₀₃:

There is no significant relationship between managements' punctuality supervision and staffs' job performance in high institutions in Sokoto state

Table 8: Relationship between Managements' Punctuality Supervision and Staffs' Job Performance in High Institutions in Sokoto State

Variable	N	\bar{x}	Df	Sig-Value	P-Value	Decision
Punctuality Supervision	291	1.0	0.05	0.00	0.28	H ₀ Rejected
Job Performance	291	0.00				

Source: Primary Data (2024)

Table 11 show that at 0.05 level of accuracy, the computed values are sig-value 0.00 and P-value 0.28 respectively; since the computed P-value is greater than the tabulated value, thus the hypothesis was rejected. Thus there is relationship between managements' punctuality supervision and staffs' job performance in high institutions in Sokoto state.

DISCUSSION

Based on the research questions answered and analyzed, the study discusses the result of the findings as follows:

1. The findings from the research question one show that there is very high level of management of instructional regularity in high institutions in Sokoto state, which include attending lectures, students management, lecture halls control, regular assessment, preparation of materials, coordination of lectures, students/lecturers attitude, familiarization with course, record keeping and preparation of exams. This is in line with Ugiomoh, Ememe, and Obike (2018), who stated that maintenance includes the physical elements of the material and non-material, the aesthetics of the whether or not it has a heat-reduction system are all the government concern in order to make the administrative effectiveness more colourful as well as students' performance.
2. The findings from the research question two also indicated that there is high level of regularity managements' of facilities supervision in high institutions in Sokoto state which include management of roofing of building, building repainting, walls, floors, windows, doors, students' and lecturers seat, ceilings, white boards and ceiling fans which is also in high in level of management. This is in line with Oluwaniyi and Oyelude (2020) who opines that management of library has to do with the collection of books and other forms of recorded information purposefully selected and systematically organized and preserved by qualified library personnel for use by either the public or a target group. Similarly, Aina and

Ogundipe (2013) posited that preservation is the maintenance of library information materials so that they can be closed to the original condition as much as possible.

3. The findings from the research question three show that there is high level of regularity of managements' punctuality supervision in high institutions in Sokoto state which include the management of Attend lecture in time, Submit C.A in time, Attendance of meeting, Distribute material regularly, Organizing seminars regularly, Assessing students at regular time, Following schedules accordingly, Perform responsibilities as schedule, Preservation of source and Marking script at prompt time. This indicated that management of punctuality is at very high level. According to Muhkti and Arikunto (2019) management of punctuality that adhere to standards is evident in higher test scores, and management of facilities that do so reflect high-quality schools. They further elaborated that complete infrastructure facilities are able to provide projections to students during learning.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

The level of management of instructional regularity in high institutions in Sokoto state is at very high level, which includes attending lectures, students management, lecture halls control, regular assessment, preparation of materials, coordination of lectures, students/lecturers attitude, familiarization with course, record keeping and preparation of exams. The level of regularity managements' of facilities supervision in high institutions in Sokoto state is also at high which include management of roofing of building, building repainting, walls, floors, windows, doors, students' and lecturers seat, ceilings, white boards and ceiling fans which is also in high in level of management. Furthermore, the level of regularity of managements' punctuality supervision in high institutions in Sokoto state is at high level which include the management of Attend lecture in time, Submit C.A in time, Attendance of meeting, Distribute material regularly, Organizing seminars regularly, Assessing students at regular time, Following schedules accordingly, Perform responsibilities as schedule, Preservation of source and Marking script at prompt time.

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations are provided.

That the management should always ensure their responsibility as the directors of the activities in the institutions that they always supervised the facilities in their school for proper use and maintenance. They should report any difficult situation concerning the school facilities to the state ministry of education for immediate intervention. Training and retraining of staff concerning school management should be organized by the state ministry of education for the subordinate to acquire more skills concerning school administrative effectiveness.

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